

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF COMMUNICATION SERVICES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SERVICE SECTOR

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Abstract. In this article, the role and importance of communication services in the development of the service sector, the formation of consumer culture in the provision of communication services, and the involvement of digital technologies in the field have been highlighted by the author.

Keywords: service, communication services, digital economy, business processes.

To date, there is no comprehensive definition of services. In determining a certain description according to its socio-economic essence, the description of services in terms of their social significance and economic result, in contrast to material goods, is of particular importance. In this case, the activity related to meeting people's needs is considered as an important feature of services, and it is manifested in the form of the final result of a concrete form or type of activity.

The category of "service" is defined by economists of Western European countries as follows: in particular, F. Kotler defines services as a wide variety of activities and commercial activities, which "can be offered by one party to another and basically, they are intangible and do not lead to ownership. The provision of services may or may not be related to tangible goods.

According to the definition given by T. Khilla, service is a change in the state of a person or goods belonging to an economic unit as a result of the activity performed by another economic unit with the prior consent of the first unit. This

definition makes it possible to consider services as the result of a clearly useful economic activity and makes the service a subject of exchange and trade.

According to the definition given by N.A. Barinov, "service is a useful action of a product (thing) or an activity that manifests itself in the form of an activity to satisfy specific, reasonable needs of a person, and appears as a result of work that creates use values are economic relations". Therefore, the process of providing services should be considered as the process of providing services to consumers, that is, the process of meeting the needs of individuals and legal entities of any kind.

If we give a more precise definition of the concept of "service", in our opinion, "a service is the result of direct interaction between the provider and the consumer, which occurs in the useful activity of the provider to satisfy the demand of the consumer. is an economic relationship".

It should be noted that when considering the concept of service, special attention is paid to the standardization of services as one of the important means of state regulation of the services market. Service standards can be used in areas such as dry cleaning, laundry, hotel business, communication, insurance, banking, trade, transport services, and car service.

In different types of services, the ratio of intangible and tangible elements is not the same, which makes it possible to distinguish between traditional and non-traditional services.

If we consider the provision of services not only as the activity of the executor necessary to provide the service, but as a process, the following main stages can be distinguished: provision of necessary resources, technological process of execution, control making, testing, acceptance, evaluation, service process.

Quality indicators have a special place in the process of service delivery, and they are in the process of constant change and improvement. As the main basic parameters, the following can be taken: service time (the period of time during which the consumer interacts with the service provider); service completion time

(standard time for service completion).

Service activities have penetrated almost all sectors of the economy, so it is very difficult to clearly define the boundaries of the service sector. In fact, this is really a "publicization sector" of service activity, which is the main one in some sectors of the economy, and is partially involved in others, for example, in the mining and manufacturing industries. Therefore, the most important feature of the service industry is its diversity, the problem of defining its "boundaries" is very relevant for statistical science and practice, because the uncertainty of the interpretation of this phenomenon is directly manifested when it reflects the structure of the national and world economy, economic The rating of a certain country is determined based on the results of development, the quality of its economic growth and the life of the population, the entire range of economic activities, economic processes at various levels, including the consistency and integration of statistical data on certain sectors and regions of the economy. .

The provision of services began to have a significant share in the structure of the gross domestic product of countries with developed market economies.

All over the world, the services industry is going through a phase of changes of a revolutionary nature, in which traditional business models are becoming less and less viable. At the beginning of the new millennium, under the influence of new trends in the field of services, people's life and work methods are undergoing drastic changes. Constantly, new methods of meeting the needs in this field are being invented, and ways to meet the needs that people could not imagine existed until recently are also emerging.

In conclusion, it can be said that the socio-economic development of communication service enterprises implies compliance with the basic rules in the implementation of goals and tasks. Accordingly, taking into account the specific characteristics of the service sector, the main principles of the development of enterprises and organizations operating in this sector are as follows:

1. The principle of goal orientation of service activities. This principle consists in the realization of the goals of ensuring socio-economic development in enterprises providing communication services. In the process of effective use of economic resources, it determines the directions for improving the efficiency of communication services, taking into account the general and specific characteristics of the tasks that must be implemented.

2. The principle of compliance with the final results of the service provider and the buyer. It is necessary to distinguish the final result of the work of the provider of communication services and the end result of the customer's work (the final result of the service). The complexity lies in the fact that the goals, interests and resources of the service provider and its customer are often not aligned or clearly defined. In order to fight against the inconsistency between the final results of the relationship between the provider of communication services and the customer, it is necessary to implement the following measures: legal support of communication services; risk insurance; certification and standardization of communication services and certain procedures; introduction of special procedures for control of execution quality; time control; analysis of complaints and suggestions; to carry out a comparative analysis of competitors for the provision of these services.

3. The principle of ensuring the compatibility of supply and demand in the services market. Maintenance of services is not considered important in the conditions of stability of demand in the market of communication services. However, as a result of changes in demand, there are difficulties and problems related to the profitability of the enterprise's services and activities. Diversification, classification of communication services, methods of forming preliminary orders are intended, first of all, to influence the external environment of the enterprise. By influencing the factors of the internal environment of the enterprise (employees, resources, working hours), it is possible to coordinate the volume of supply and

demand for communication services, to use resources effectively, and to increase the profitability of the enterprise.

4. Transversality principle of service market development. This principle includes the elimination of infrastructural and institutional limitations in the field of communication services, the development and implementation of targeted programs for the development of regional economic relations, and the integration of traditions and innovations in the development of the service sector. takes

5. Ensuring continuous growth of labor productivity in the service sector. This principle allows social and economic development of communication service enterprises, achieving compatibility of supply and demand for produced services, and ensuring sustainable economic development.

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